

Thermodynamics of the transition from the ferryl (F) state to the oxidized form of the solubilized cytochrome *c* oxidase: implication for the proton pumping

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Abbreviations

CcO – cytochrome *c* oxidase, **O** – oxidized CcO, **F** -ferryl intermediate of CcO, Fe_a – iron of cytochrome *a*, Fe_{a3} – iron of cytochrome *a*₃, Fe_c – iron of cytochrome *c*, *c*^{II} - ferrocycytochrome *c*, *c*^{III} - ferricytochrome *c*, Fe_m^{II} - ferrocenemethanol, Fe_m^{III} - ferroceniummethanol, Fe_{CN}^{II} - ferrocyanide, Fe_{CN}^{III} - ferricyanide, eu – entropy unit (cal/mol K), E₀ – electrode potential, ET – electron transfer, DFT – density functional theory.

ABSTRACT

Two ferryl intermediates have been identified in the membrane-bound respiratory heme-copper oxygen reductases (HCOs) during reduction of O₂ to water. Apparently, energy released by reduction of these two ferryl forms is utilized to build the transmembrane electrochemical proton gradient by two mechanisms. One of them, the proton pumping, is the key unresolved problem of the contemporary molecular bioenergetics. Even though the position of these ferryl forms in energy transformation is central, the direct and complete thermodynamic characterization of these intermediates is lacking. Here, thermodynamics of redox transition of one of these ferryl intermediates, the **F** state, was established by isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC) and density functional theory utilizing one representative of HCOs, bovine cytochrome *c* oxidase (CcO). In CcOs, the reduction of catalytic cytochrome *a*₃-Cu_B center is accomplished by electron transfer (ET) from ferrocyanochrome *c* via copper Cu_A and cytochrome *a* center. The energy for the pumping is suggested to be released mainly during the transition of the catalytic center of **F** initiated by ET from cytochrome *a*. This transfer results in the conversion of Fe(IV)=O to Fe(III) state of heme *a*₃, yielding the oxidized CcO (**O**). Based on the enthalpy changes determined by ITC and available entropy values for this process, the estimated ΔG^0 was found to be -24 kcal/mol, corresponding to the electrode potential of +1.3 V for the **F/O** couple (pH 8.0, 25 °C). Remarkably, the results indicate that major fraction of energy for the proton pumping is provided by the redox-dependent structural changes of cytochrome *a*.

Graphical Abstract

INTRODUCTION

Activation of oxygen in biological systems is achieved by metal centers (mostly iron and copper) found in metalloenzymes. This activation, occurring in heme and non-heme iron-containing enzymes, is accomplished by the transient formation of the high-valent iron(IV)-oxo intermediates (ferryl species). These high-valent systems are observed in catalysis of variety of heme enzymes like peroxidases, heme catalases, oxygenases, halogenases and respiratory oxygen reductases [1-11].

Most of the membrane-bound respiratory oxidases belong to the superfamily of heme-copper oxygen reductases (HCOs) [12-14]. The energy released during the reduction of dioxygen to water by HCOs is utilized to build the transmembrane electrochemical proton gradient by two distinct mechanisms. One of these mechanisms, proton pumping, remains an essential unresolved issue in the contemporary molecular bioenergetics.

A large family of HCOs includes cytochrome *c* oxidases (CcOs) found in all eukaryotes and some prokaryotes [12, 13]. In this class of the enzymes, electrons for the reduction of dioxygen are provided by ferrocyanochrome *c* (c^{II}). Electrons from c^{II} are delivered to the copper Cu_A center, the first electron acceptor in CcOs. Electron transfer (ET) then proceeds intramolecularly to cytochrome *a* and finally to the binuclear catalytic cytochrome a_3 - Cu_B center (Fig. 1), where O_2 is sequentially reduced to H_2O by four electrons.

Apparently, the main portion of energy, required for a charge translocation across the membrane against an electrochemical potential of ~ 200 mV [15, 16], is released during the ET from cytochrome *a* to certain oxy-intermediates of the catalytic center. One of these intermediates, referred to as the ferryl **F** state, is formed when three electrons are delivered to the catalytic center for the reduction of O_2 [17-22] (Fig. 2). In the **F** state, the iron of heme a_3 is in the high-valent $Fe_{a_3}^{IV}=O$ state [8, 23-25], and a water molecule is apparently bound to $Cu_B^{II}(Fe_{a_3}^{IV}=O \cdot H_2O \cdot Cu_B^{II})$ [23, 26]. Upon transfer of a single electron into the catalytic center of the **F** state, this form is converted to the fully oxidized enzyme [20, 27, 28].

It has been suggested that two different forms of the oxidized state of CcO exist. One form, denoted as **O_H**, emerges immediately after the one-electron reduction of the **F** state. The **O_H** is considered as a ‘high-energy’ metastable state in which part of the energy released during O_2 reduction is stored. This stored energy in the **O_H** is utilized for the proton pumping during the subsequent reduction of the catalytic center by two electrons. In the absence of external electron donors, the **O_H** is supposedly relaxing to the ‘resting’ (or as isolated) **O** state [16, 29-31]. After the **O_H**-to-**O** relaxation, the stored energy is dissipated as heat, and the subsequent reduction of the enzyme proceeds without proton pumping.

To elucidate the proton pumping mechanism in CcO, the determination of thermodynamic parameters of the redox transitions of the intermediates of the catalytic center, participating in charge translocation, is essential. Several theoretical studies have predicted ΔG^0 values for the transitions between oxy-intermediates of the catalytic center [32-35]. However, the experimental determination of

ΔG^0 for these transitions relies only on the indirect and complex approach of utilizing the energization of mitochondria with ATP [15, 36]. In particular, the ΔG^0 for the $\mathbf{F} \rightarrow \mathbf{O}_H$ transition was estimated from reverse ET, stimulated by mitochondrial energization [15, 16, 31, 36, 37]. Nevertheless, the thermodynamic characterization of the complete $\mathbf{F} \rightarrow \mathbf{O}$ conversion, including the energy lost by the potential relaxation of $\mathbf{O}_H \rightarrow \mathbf{O}$, is lacking.

In this study, the enthalpy changes associated with the complete $\mathbf{F} \rightarrow \mathbf{O}_H \rightarrow \mathbf{O}$ transformation of the isolated bovine heart CcO were directly measured by the isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC) and also evaluated by the density functional theory calculations. The contributions of enthalpic and entropic terms to the ΔG of the $\mathbf{F} \rightarrow \mathbf{O}$ transition, as well as the implications of these findings for the proton pumping mechanism are discussed. Furthermore, the ITC method allowed to establish the net number of protons consumed from solution during the \mathbf{F} -to- \mathbf{O} conversion.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials. The detergent Triton X-100 (TX) was purchased from Across and hydrogen peroxide solution (~30%) was from Fluka. All other chemicals were obtained from Merck. Bovine heart cytochrome c oxidase (CcO) was isolated in 2 mM potassium phosphate buffer (KPi), pH 8.0, 50 mM K_2SO_4 and 0.1 % TX according to a published method [38]. The purified enzyme (~200 μM) was frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80°C . The concentration of the oxidized CcO was determined from its optical absorption spectrum using an extinction coefficient $\varepsilon(424\text{ nm}) = 156\text{ mM}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ [39].

Formation and reduction of the ferryl \mathbf{F} form. Two procedures are available for the formation of the \mathbf{F} state. One is the reaction of three-electron reduced CcO with O_2 . The other protocol is based on the reaction of the \mathbf{O} state with an excess of H_2O_2 (mM). The equivalence of these two ferryl forms has been validated by their identical optical absorption spectra [40-42], resonance Raman characteristics [43-45] [20, 24, 25] and the similar stoichiometry of the charge translocation during the $\mathbf{F} \rightarrow \mathbf{O}_H$ conversion [21, 46-52].

In this work, the peroxide-induced \mathbf{F} state was utilized. This \mathbf{F} intermediate was produced from 30 μM oxidized CcO (\mathbf{O}) in buffer (38 mM KPi, pH 8.0, 15 mM K_2SO_4 , 0.2 % TX) by reaction with 2.2 mM H_2O_2 for 30 s at ambient temperature. This sample was then immersed in an ice-water bath followed by the addition of catalase (final concentration 4 μM) and superoxidase dismutase (300 Units/ml) to eliminate residual H_2O_2 and superoxide, respectively. One-electron reduction of the \mathbf{F} intermediate was performed by using a sub-stoichiometric concentration of ferrocenemethanol (Fe_m^{2+}) (10 μM) with ~14 μM horse heart ferricytochrome *c* (c^{III}) serving as the electron transfer mediator. The concentration of the \mathbf{F} state was calculated from the $\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{O}$ difference absorption spectrum using $\Delta\varepsilon(580\text{-}630\text{ nm}) = 5.3\text{ mM}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ [15].

Typically, the concentration of the **F** state produced by this protocol was about 23 μM (77 %) while the remaining 7 μM) was present in the oxidized form. Thus, to avoid possible turnover, only electron donors with high reduction potentials ($\sim 400\text{mV}$) can be used for the selective one-electron reduction of the **F** state [53].

Spectroscopic measurements. The diode-array S600 UV-Vis spectrometer equipped with a thermostated cell holder was used for these measurements. The spectra and kinetics of **F** reduction, initiated by the injection of Fe_m^{II} were obtained from the accumulated spectra in the range of 400 - 700 nm. Spectra were recorded every 10 s and the kinetics of reduction of the iron(IV)-oxo state of heme a_3 was derived from the time-dependent changes in $\Delta A(580\text{-}630\text{ nm})$.

Calorimetric measurements. The enthalpy change (ΔH), i.e., the released heat, associated with the **F**-to-**O** conversion triggered by one-electron reduction, was determined using a Microcal ITC200 isothermal titration calorimeter. The ITC cell was filled with the **F** intermediate and 2 μl of 1 mM ferrocenemethanol (Fe_m^{II}) was delivered in a single injection over 4 s, with a stirring speed of 300 rpm. Calorimetric measurements were performed at 5 $^\circ\text{C}$ in three different buffers (KPi, Tricine and Tris), all adjusted to pH 8.0 and ionic strength of $I = 0.145$. The composition of the individual buffers was as follows: 38 mM KPi, 15 mM K_2SO_4 ; 38 mM Tricine, 39 mM K_2SO_4 and 38 mM Tris, 42 mM K_2SO_4 .

The ionization enthalpies of these buffers were established using the same composition as described above. A volume of 2 μl of 10 mM HCl was injected into the calorimetric cell filled with either KPi buffer at pH 8.0; Tricine at pH 8.5 or Tris at pH 8.6. The heat of dilution was assessed by injecting 2 μl of 10 mM HCl prepared in 150 mM KCl into the cell filled with 150 mM KCl containing 1 mM HCl. The following ionization enthalpies were obtained at 5 $^\circ\text{C}$ for the ionization reaction: phosphate (second ionization), $+ 2.1 \pm 0.2\text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ ($1.2 \pm 0.2\text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ at 25 $^\circ\text{C}$); Tricine, $+ 7.9 \pm 0.2\text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$; and Tris, $11.9 \pm 0.4\text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$.

The temperature dependence of the reaction enthalpy for the reduction of **F** by c^{II} was determined in phosphate buffer at 5, 10, 15 and 20 $^\circ\text{C}$. This temperature range was limited by the increased instability of the **F** state at higher temperatures. This instability is consequence of the enhanced rate of endogenous reduction of **F** - i.e., its conversion to the oxidized form of CcO - due to intrinsic electron transfer arising from the oxidation of the enzyme, which becomes more pronounced with increasing temperature [53].

To establish the ΔH for the reduction of **F** by c^{II} , two additional reaction enthalpies were measured: the oxidation of c^{II} by ferricyanide ($\text{Fe}_{\text{CN}}^{\text{III}}$) and the reduction of $\text{Fe}_{\text{CN}}^{\text{III}}$ by Fe_m^{II} . In the first case, 20 μM c^{II} in the ITC cell was oxidized by the injection of 92 μM $\text{Fe}_{\text{CN}}^{\text{III}}$. In the second measurements, the reduction of $\text{Fe}_{\text{CN}}^{\text{III}}$ was achieved by the injection of 20.5 μM $\text{Fe}_{\text{CN}}^{\text{III}}$ into a solution containing 200 μM Fe_m^{II} in the cell. Separate measurements of heats of dilution were performed, and appropriate corrections were applied for the dilution of ferricyanide in buffer. The heats of dilution of c^{II} and Fe_m^{II} were found to be negligible.

Full oxidation of c^{II} was verified by UV-vis absorption spectra collected before and after each ITC measurement. From the c^{II} - c^{III} difference spectra the concentration of c^{II} oxidized in the ITC cell was calculated using $\Delta\epsilon(550\text{-}542\text{ nm}) = 20\text{ mM}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ [54]. The full reduction of $20.5\text{ }\mu\text{M Fe}_{\text{CN}}^{\text{III}}$ was accomplished by $200\text{ }\mu\text{M Fe}_{\text{m}}^{\text{II}}$. All above ITC measurements were carried out in 38 mM KPi , $\text{pH } 8.0$, $15\text{ mM K}_2\text{SO}_4$, 0.2 \% TX .

Molar entropy change for ferro- to ferricytochrome c transition ($S_{\text{cIII}} - S_{\text{cII}}$). The value of ($S_{\text{cIII}} - S_{\text{cII}}$) under present conditions (38 mM KPi , $\text{pH } 8.0$, $20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $I = 0.145$ adjusted with K_2SO_4), was established by combination of two approaches. The first involved determining the temperature coefficient of the reduction potential (dE_0/dT) of $\text{Fe}_{\text{CN}}^{\text{III}}/\text{Fe}_{\text{CN}}^{\text{II}}$ couple, and the second was the establishment of the equilibrium constant for the reduction of c^{III} by $\text{Fe}_{\text{CN}}^{\text{II}}$. Using these two determinations, the value of ($S_{\text{cIII}} - S_{\text{cII}}$) was found to be $+12.1\text{ eu}$ ($+27.7\text{ eu vs NHE}$) at $20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (see SI). This value agrees well with that previously reported for horse heart cytochrome c under standard conditions ($I = 0.1$, $\text{pH } 7.0$, $25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) [14, 55].

Density functional theory (DFT) calculations. All calculations of the model structure of the catalytic center in the **F** and the **O** state were performed with the program ORCA 5.0 (46). Geometry optimizations were done with the B3LYP functional (47) used for calculations of the active site in several previous studies (23, 48, 49), the D3 dispersion corrections (50) and the def2-SVP basis set on all atoms except for iron and copper which had the def2-TZVP basis set (51). Frequency calculations were performed at the same level of theory with thermal corrections at 298 K to retrieve the enthalpies. Single point energy calculations were performed with the def2-TZVP basis set on all atoms and this energy was used for the electronic energy contribution of the enthalpy calculations. The CPCM solvation model (52) was used for all calculations with the dielectric constant set to $\epsilon = 4$ (53). Enthalpic contributions from the oxidation of cytochrome c were considered in absolute terms using the absolute potential of the normal hydrogen electrode (NHE) of 4.43 V (54) and for the proton donation the standard enthalpy of formation for $\text{H}^+(\text{g})$ of 368.69 kcal/mol (55) was used.

Coordinates of the binuclear center, extracted from PDB 7COH [56], were truncated for DFT calculations. All the three histidines coordinating the Cu_{B} , the proximal histidine of heme a_3 , as well as the active site tyrosine were truncated at the β -carbon. The porphyrin of heme a_3 was truncated with methyl groups on all non-aromatic substituents except for the inclusion of the farnesyl hydroxyl group. Seven carbons were frozen to approximate the constrained nature of the active site. These carbons were the β -carbons of the copper coordinating histidines, the β -carbon of the tyrosine, as well as three of the methyl groups of the heme a_3 .

The **F** state of the active site was modelled as an oxoferryl heme group ($\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}=\text{O}$). The Cu_{B} -tyrosine part of the system was modelled either a water molecule coordinating the copper and the tyrosine deprotonated ($\text{Fe}(\text{IV})=\text{O} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}-\text{Cu}$, TyrO^-) or the copper coordinated by a hydroxide with the tyrosine being protonated ($\text{Fe}(\text{IV})=\text{O} \cdot \text{HO}-\text{Cu}$, TyrOH). The **O** state was modelled as a ferric iron with

a hydroxide ligand and a water coordinating the copper and the tyrosine being deprotonated (Fe(III)-OH⁻ H₂O-Cu, TyrO⁻). All systems yield a total charge of +1, which is thought to be charge compensated for by the propionate anion of the heme *a*₃ not included in this system. The system consisted of 131 atoms for the ferryl **F** states with one extra hydrogen atom for the **O** state.

RESULTS

One-electron reduction of the ferryl **F** intermediate of CcO is illustrated in Figure 3. The injection of 10 μM Fe_m^{II} (final concentration) (Fig. 3, Fe²⁺ arrow) into 23 μM **F** (in KPi buffer, pH 8.0, 5 °C), triggers the disappearance of this state monitored selectively by the spectral change ΔA(580-630 nm). However, the observed loss of **F** proceeds in two phases: a rapid phase corresponding to the reduction of the **F** by the added electron donor, and a slower phase due to the reduction of iron(IV)-oxo of heme *a*₃ by the autoxidation of the enzyme [53]. A two-exponential fit of the reduction kinetics showed that the reduction by Fe_m^{II} is about ten times faster (time constant τ₁ ≈ 32 s) than the spontaneous decay (τ₂ ≈ 300 s). The rate of the slow phase corresponds to that observed during the spontaneous transition of the **F** to oxidized CcO observed in the absence of external electron donor (not shown). From the spectral amplitude of the fast phase (ΔA=0.01), it was calculated that 9.9 μM **F** was reduced by 10 μM Fe_m^{II}.

The reduction of **F** state and the formation of the oxidized CcO (**O**) during the rapid phase are also illustrated in the Figure 3 (inset). The difference spectrum, obtained by subtracting the spectrum recorded 200 s after the injection from that collected immediately before the injection of Fe_m^{II} corresponds to the **F**-*minus*-**O** spectrum with characteristic maxima at 580 nm and 434 nm, and a minimum at 413 nm [42, 57]. The kinetics and spectral changes were not affected by the choice of buffer (KPi, Tris, Tricine).

The one-electron reduction of the **F** state in these three buffers, initiated by injection of Fe_m^{II}, each with a different ionization enthalpy (ΔH_{BI}), was also examined at 5 °C using isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC) (Fig. 4). Since the **F**-to-**O** transition is associated with the uptake of protons from the solution, the observed enthalpy change ΔH_{obs} consists of two components: the reaction enthalpy (ΔH_{rc}) and the buffer ionization enthalpy (ΔH_{BI}) multiplied by the number of protons (n) taken up from the solution during the reduction of the **F** form (ΔH_{obs} = ΔH_{rc} + n ΔH_{BI}). Integration of the obtained ITC traces (Fig. 4A) yielded the ΔH_{obs} values in each buffer for the following reaction:

The slope of 0.85 ± 0.08 of the linear dependence of ΔH_{obs} vs ΔH_{BI} (Fig. 4B) indicates that approximately one proton is consumed from the solution during this process. The reaction enthalpy changes ΔH_{rc} for the studied process, obtained by extrapolating the fitted line to ΔH_{BI} = 0, is -13.6 ± 0.7 kcal/mol.

The temperature dependence of ΔH_{rc} (Fig. 5, blue points), measured in KPi buffer, was obtained by subtracting the ionization enthalpy of this buffer (ΔH_{BI}) from the ΔH_{obs}, assuming the uptake of one

H⁺ from the solution during the **F**-to-**O** conversion, initiated by electron transfer from Fe_m^{II} ($\Delta H_{rc} = \Delta H_{obs} - \Delta H_{BI}$). The published ΔH_{BI} values for KPi [58] were utilized in our calculations since the ionization enthalpies of this buffer at 5 and 25 °C, determined under the present experimental conditions, were nearly coincidental with those determined previously.

To establish the reaction enthalpy and its temperature for the reduction of the **F** by ferrocycochrome *c*

the determination of the reaction enthalpies of two other redox reactions was performed. One was the oxidation of *c*^{II} by an excess of ferricyanide (Fe_{CN}^{III}) and the other reduction of Fe_{CN}^{III} by an excess of Fe_m^{II} (see Figure S1). Altogether, the temperature dependencies of three enthalpies, associated with the sequence of electron transfers *c* → Fe_{CN} → Fe_m → **F**, were determined. The sum of these three enthalpies provided the enthalpy change for the reaction (2) and temperature dependence (Fig. 5, red data). From the linear extrapolation of this dependence, the reaction enthalpy at 25 °C was found to be -13.6 kcal/mol and -12.6 kcal/mol at physiological temperature (37°C). The heat capacity change (ΔC_p) associated with this reaction is +82 cal/mol K.

The **F**-to-**O** transition, induced by ferrocycochrome *c*, was also examined by the density functional theory calculations as well. Two structural states of the catalytic center of this intermediate, [Fe^{IV}=O H₂O-Cu^{II}, TyrO⁻] and [Fe^{IV}=O ·HO-Cu^{II} TyrOH], were selected for the calculation. This selection is substantiated by the recently determined structure of the oxidized bovine CcO in which hydroxide ion is bound to Fe(III) of heme *a*₃ with a water molecule apparently coordinated to Cu_B(II) [23] and Tyr244 is deprotonated [59]. Consequently, the investigated two structures of the **F** appear as the most likely outcome of the reverse **O**-to-**F** conversion, achieved by one electron transfer and one proton dissociation from the catalytic center. The result of this computation revealed the good agreement between the experimentally determined ΔH of -13.6 kcal/mol (25°C) and the computed ΔH of -15.6 kcal/mol for [Fe^{IV}=O H₂O-Cu^{II}, TyrO⁻] → [Fe^{III}-OH⁻ H₂O-Cu^{II}, TyrO⁻] transition in which Tyr244 remains deprotonated in both states. On the other hand, the computed ΔH of -42.9 kcal/mol was obtained for the second transition of [Fe^{IV}=O ·HO-Cu^{II} TyrOH] → [Fe_{a₃}^{III}-OH⁻ H₂O-Cu^{II} TyrO⁻]. The relatively high potential energy of this **F** state is consistent with result of the earlier computational study [60].

Since the reduction of the **F** state of the isolated CcO by *c*^{II} is practically an irreversible process, direct determination of the equilibrium constant and the corresponding ΔG ($\Delta G = \Delta H - T\Delta S$) is not feasible. However, the entropy change (ΔS) can be estimated using the relation $\Delta S = (S_{cIII} - S_{cII}) + (S_O - S_F)$, where S_{cIII} , S_{cII} , S_O and S_F are the molar entropies of *c*^{III}, *c*^{II}, oxidized (**O**) and ferryl (**F**) forms, respectively.

An approximate value of ($S_O - S_F$) can be inferred from experimental data obtained for the heme proteins, where the equilibrium between the iron(IV)-oxo ↔ iron(III)-OH⁻ states is established [61, 62], as well as from the computational studies of intermediates within CcO families [33]. Both types of the

investigations indicate that the standard entropy change for this reaction is small. The entropy change of $+4.2 \pm 3.9$ eu (0.1 M KPi, pH 7.0, 25 °C) was reported for the transition of horseradish peroxidase Compound II to its ferric state [61] and $+6.7$ eu ($I = 0$, pH 7.0, 25 °C) was determined for the ferryl-to-ferric myoglobin conversion [62]. Furthermore, calculated entropy effects ($T\Delta S$) for the redox transitions of the catalytic center of CcO, where no small molecules enter or leave the catalytic center, were about a couple of kcal/mol [33].

Thus, taking the established entropy change $\Delta S = +27.7$ eu (vs NHE) for c^{II} to c^{III} conversion and $\Delta S = +5$ eu (vs NHE) for ($S_{\text{O}} - S_{\text{F}}$), an average of the determined values for the ferryl-to-ferric transitions of horseradish peroxidase and myoglobin, the Gibbs free energy change associated with the reduction of the **F** form by c^{II} is -23.6 kcal/mol ($+1.03$ eV) at 25 °C. Considering the electrode potential of $+260$ mV (vs NHE) for horse heart cytochrome *c* [14, 54], the corresponding potential of the **F/O** couple is $+1.3$ V (pH 8.0, $I = 0.145$).

DISCUSSION

As indicated by the previous studies, the reduction of the **F** state is associated with the transfer of two elementary charges across the membrane [21, 46-52, 63-66]. The transfer of an electron from one side of the membrane, coupled with the uptake of one substrate proton from the opposite side for water formation at the catalytic center, accounts for translocation of one charge. Proton pumping, during which one proton is translocated through the membrane in the same direction as the substrate proton, corresponds to the second charge transfer [21, 46-52, 63-66]. Since these charge translocation are observed on the milliseconds timescale, they can be assigned to the **F** \rightarrow **O_H** transition [67]. The nearly one H^+ uptake observed in this work by ITC (Fig. 4), using solubilized enzyme, is most likely a consequence of the consumption of two protons from solution and the release of one pumped proton into the medium.

An additional proton is suggested to be transferred into the $\text{Fe}_{\text{a}_3}\text{-Cu}_{\text{B}}$ center during the proposed spontaneous **O_H** \rightarrow **O** relaxation [23, 35]. The current calorimetric measurements, performed with solubilized enzyme over a time period sufficient for the complete **F** \rightarrow **O_H** \rightarrow **O** transition [67], showed only a single H^+ uptake from the buffer (Fig. 4). The absence of consumption of this additional proton from the solution, as monitored by a pH indicator following the reoxidation of fully reduced CcO with O_2 , is also supported by our previous study [68]. Consequently, protonation of a group at the catalytic center during the **O_H**-to-**O** relaxation may occur via an internal proton transfer. Alternatively, the protonation state of $\text{Fe}_{\text{a}_3}\text{-Cu}_{\text{B}}$ center may be the same in the **O_H** and **O** forms.

Reduction of the iron(IV)-oxo state of heme *a*₃, coupled with the proton transfer to the catalytic center of the **F** form results in the conversion of $\text{Fe}_{\text{a}_3}^{\text{IV}}=\text{O}$ to $\text{Fe}_{\text{a}_3}^{\text{III}}\text{-OH}^-$, as identified by resonance Raman spectroscopy [23-25]. Since one molecule of water apparently remains bound to $\text{Cu}_{\text{B}}^{\text{II}}$ in both

the **O_H** and **O** forms [23], the transition of **F**-to-**O** at the catalytic center can be represented by the following reaction:

The reduction of the ferryl heme *a*₃ in the **F** state by ferrocytochrome *c* is accomplished through two intramolecular ET steps: Cu_A → Fe_a → Fe_{a₃}-Cu_B. The available thermodynamic data for these redox transitions (vs NHE), including the present data for the reduction of the **F** state, are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Experimental redox thermodynamic parameters of cytochrome *c* and the metal centers of cytochrome *c* oxidase

Redox center	ΔG ⁰ (kcal/mol)	ΔH ⁰ (kcal/mol)	ΔS ⁰ (cal/mol K)	-TΔS ⁰ (kcal/mol)
Fe _c ^a	-6.0	-14.5	-28.0	8.3
Cu _A ^b	-6.6	-21.1	-48.7	14.5
Fe _a ^c	-7.9	-22.7	-50.0	14.9
Fe _{a₃} (IV)=O ^d (F)	-29.6	-28.1	+5	-1.49

^a [14, 55]; ^b [69]; ^c [70]; ^d This work (pH 8.0, 25 °C and I = 0.145). E₀(F/O) = +1.3 V assuming E₀(c) = +260 mV; ΔS is an average of the values obtained for horseradish peroxidase [61] and myoglobin [62].

The Gibbs free energy released during ET from cytochrome *c* (Fe_c) to Cu_A and subsequently to heme *a* (Fe_a) is relatively small (-1.9 kcal/mol). Given the E₀(Fe_a^{III}/Fe_a^{II}) ≈ 0.3 V [54], the major release of the energy is associated with the ET from Fe_a^{II} to Fe_{a₃}^{IV}=O (-21.7 kcal/mol, 0.94 eV).

Importantly, this redox reaction is linked with the translocation of charges, proton pumping and the uptake of proton to the catalytic center [29, 71-74]. Most remarkable, however, is the partitioning of the free energy (0.94 eV) between enthalpic and the entropic terms. A major fraction of this energy is entropic in nature (TΔS = -16.4 kcal/mol, 0.71 eV), while a smaller portion is enthalpic (-5.4 kcal/mol, 0.23 eV). Notably, nearly 70% of this free energy is supplied by the entropy change of cytochrome *a*. These entropy changes, accompanying the redox transition of cytochrome *a*, are also supported by X-ray structures of CcO [75-77]. The structural changes in heme *a* itself, together with alteration in segment of helix X (Val 380, Leu 381 and Ser 382, bovine numbering) of subunit I which is located between heme *a* and heme *a*₃ in CcO, have been observed [75]. These transitions are responsible for a reversible opening of the water channel, connecting heme *a* with the mitochondrial matrix [75] and plausibly as well for the water molecules to move in and out of CcO [78].

The established $E_0(\mathbf{F}/\mathbf{O}) \approx +1.3$ V is approximately 300 mV higher than the values observed for the similar transitions of compound II/ferric state of hemes in horseradish peroxidase [61, 79], *Arthromyces ramosus* peroxidase [80], cytochrome *c* peroxidase [81], cytochrome P450 [82] and myoglobin [62]. This higher reduction potential may result from several additive effects. One obvious contributing factor is the presence of heme *a* in CcO, in contrast to protoheme IX found in the other enzymes [83, 84]. An additional effect may arise from differences in the dielectric constant of the heme environment, which can shift the E_0 in the range of 0.5 V [83]. Furthermore, the E_0 value is sensitive not only to the number of water molecules in the vicinity of heme, but also to their orientation [84] and to the degree of heme exposure to the aqueous solvent [85, 86].

According to the present data, the energy released by ET from cytochrome *a* to the catalytic center in the **F** form is ~ 1 eV. If the **F**-to-**O_H** transition were associated with the translocation of two charges across the membrane [21, 46-52, 63-66], against a membrane potential of 200 mV, the residual energy accumulated in the **O_H** state would be 0.6 eV. Since the reduction potentials of both heme *a*₃ and Cu_B in both **O** and **O_H** forms of CcO are similar [87, 88], this energy might be stored in a non-equilibrium structure of oxidized cytochrome *a* produced immediately after ET to the catalytic center in the **F** state. This assignment is implicated by the substantial structural (entropic) changes that accompany the redox transition of cytochrome *a*.

The redox-dependent structural changes of cytochrome *a* represent in some models the part of the mechanism of proton pumping [76, 89]. However, these changes were also suggested to merely facilitate the transient ET through the buried heme *a*, potentially modulating the electron flow through this cofactor [90]. However, without the structural/entropic contribution of cytochrome *a*, the Gibbs free energy available from the reduction of the **F** form would be approximately 0.3 eV (25 °C, pH 8.0). In that case, the translocation of two or more charges, supported by this energy, would be feasible only if the membrane potential were below 200 mV. Clearly, including the entropic contribution associated with the transition of cytochrome *a* in the total free energy is essential for enabling CcO to pump protons against this potential.

Altogether, the present calorimetric data are consistent with the uptake of one proton from the solution into the catalytic Fe_{a3}-Cu_B center during the **F**-to-**O** conversion of the detergent solubilized cytochrome *c* oxidase. Importantly, the main fraction of the energy available from the reduction of the **F** state that may be used for charge translocation is entropic in nature. In particular, the entropy changes accompanying the redox transition of cytochrome *a* are a significant contributor to the Gibbs free energy of this reaction. The present results indicate that the mainly structural changes of cytochrome *a* and possibly the coupling of these structural alterations with the redox transition of the catalytic center of the oxidase are indispensable for the proton pumping mechanism.

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FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1. Structure of the catalytic heme a_3 -Cu_B center of the oxidized bovine heart cytochrome c oxidase. Cu_B (cyano sphere) is coordinated by His291, His290 and His240. His240 is covalently bound to Tyr244. The electron density between the iron of heme a_3 and Cu_B was modeled as a hydroxide ion bound to the iron and H₂O coordinated to the copper (red spheres) (PDB ID: 8GCQ).

Figure 2. Plausible catalytic cycle of CcO. Oval boxes describe the states of binuclear Fe_{a3}- Cu_B center (BNC). The name of each state is indicated above the upper right corner. Y – refers to Tyr244 that is covalently bound to one of the three histidine ligands of Cu_B. Transitions between intermediates are indicated by blue hollow arrows. Binding of O₂ to the reduced Fe_{a3}- Cu_B center (**R**) results in the formation of compound **A** followed by the split of O-O bond that produces the ferryl **P_M** intermediate. In this ferryl form, Tyr244 radical (Y[•]) is generated as well. In the next four catalytic transitions, the **P_M** to the second ferryl **F** state, the **F** to the proposed metastable oxidized form (**O_H**), the **O_H** to one-electron reduced form (**E_H**) and finally from **E_H** to **R** state, one electron and proton are transferred into BNC. In addition, these four redox transitions are associated with the translocation of one proton across the membrane (dashed brown arrow). In the absence of external electron donors, the **O_H** state is supposed to relax to the second oxidized form (**O**) (resting form) with the dissipation of stored energy in the form of heat.

Figure 3. Reduction of the ferryl **F** intermediate by a single electron monitored by optical absorption spectroscopy. The kinetics of the reduction of 23 μM **F** form, registered as the spectral change ΔA(580-630 nm), was initiated by the injection of 10 μM ferrocenemethanol (Fe²⁺ arrow) at pH 8.0 and 5 °C. Inset: Difference spectrum between the spectra recorded immediately before and 200 s after the injection of ferrocenemethanol. Measurement conditions: 38 mM buffer, 15 mM K₂SO₄, pH 8.0, 0.2 % TX, 0.4 μM catalase, 300 Units/ml superoxide dismutase, 14.3 μM ferricytochrome *c* and 5 °C.

Figure 4. Determination of the reaction enthalpy and number of protons consumed during the transition of the ferryl **F** form to the oxidized oxidase by isothermal titration calorimetry. **(A)** Calorimetric traces recorded after the injection of 10 μM ferrocenemethanol (Fe²⁺ arrow) into a cell containing 23 μM **F** form in phosphate, Tris and Tricine buffers. **(B)** Dependence of the observed reaction enthalpy changes on the ionization enthalpy of these buffers. The slope of the linear fit of the data (dashed line) is 0.85± 0.08. For measurement conditions see Materials and methods.

Figure 5. Temperature dependence of the reaction enthalpies for the conversion of the **F** form to oxidized cytochrome oxidase initiated by reduction with ferrocenemethanol and ferrocycytochrome *c*.

Blue data – reduction with ferrocenemethanol. Red data – reduction with ferrocycytochrome *c*. From linear fits of these dependencies, heat capacity changes (ΔC_p) changes of $+63 \pm 14$ and $+82 \pm 50$ cal/mol K were derived for reduction with ferrocenemethanol and ferrocycytochrome *c*, respectively. For measurement conditions see Materials and methods.

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Figure 1

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